

BEYOND ORNAMENTATION: THE PHARMACOLOGICAL WONDERS OF *lantana camara linn*

N. Astalakshmi, S. Snegapriya, S. Srivishnu, R. Palpandi, K. Raviganesh, P. Sanchay,
M. Surendra kumar.

Senghundhar College of Pharmacy, Tiruchengode – 637205, Namakkal district,
Tamil Nadu.

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR:

Dr. N. ASTALAKSHMI

ABSTRACT

Lantana camara, a tropical shrub belonging to the Verbenaceae family, is widely recognized for its ornamental value and medicinal properties. Native to the Americas, it has become naturalized across many tropical and subtropical regions globally. The plant has long been utilized in traditional medicine for treating a variety of ailments, including skin conditions, malaria, and hypertension. Recent studies have highlighted its diverse pharmacological activities, such as antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, and antiulcerogenic effects. The plant contains a range of phytochemicals, including triterpenoids, flavonoids, and essential oils, which contribute to its therapeutic potential. Additionally, *L. camara* exhibits insecticidal, anti-thrombin, and anti-hyperglycemic properties, making it a valuable resource for both modern and traditional medicine. However, it is also considered an invasive species in many regions. This review explores the medicinal applications, phytochemical composition, and pharmacological activities of *Lantana camara*, underscoring its significance as both a therapeutic agent and a challenge for biodiversity conservation.

KEY WORDS: Verbenaceae, creatinine, pharmacological benefits, India.

INTRODUCTION

Lantana camara is regarded as one of the most significant medicinal weeds worldwide (1). The name *Lantana camara* is derived from the Latin word *lento*, meaning “to bend” (2). This species was first described and given its binomial name by Linnaeus in 1753(1). *L. camara*, a flowering species of the Verbenaceae family, is widely recognized as an ornamental garden plant. Commonly referred to as wild sage or Lantana (3), this tropical plant originates from Central and Northern South America, as well as the Caribbean. It has been documented in regions such as aico, Florida, Trinidad, Jamaica, and Brazil (4). Currently, *L. camara* has naturalized across approximately 60 countries and island regions within the latitudinal range of 35° N to 35° S, including various African nations like Kenya, Uganda, Tanzania, and South Africa (5).

Introduced to India prior to the 19th century, *L. camara* is now prevalent throughout the country. It is known by diverse regional names such as Raimuniya (Hindi), Chaturangi and Vanacehedi (Sanskrit),

Arippu and Unnichedi (Tamil), Aripooov, Poochedi, Konginipoo, and Nattachedi (Malayalam), Thirei, Samballei, and Nongballei (Manipuri), Tantani and Ghaneri (Marathi), Pulikampa (Telugu), and Kakke and Natahu (Kannada).

Plants have been utilized in traditional medicine for thousands of years. In recent decades, there has been growing interest in studying medicinal plants and their traditional applications worldwide (6). These traditional medicines involve the use of natural substances for therapeutic purposes. *Lantana camara* has long been used in traditional medicine for treating conditions such as itches, cuts, ulcers, and swellings (7).

Various parts of the plant have been employed for numerous ailments. The leaves have been traditionally used for their antitumoral, antibacterial, and antihypertensive properties, while the roots have been used to treat malaria, rheumatism, and skin rashes. The plant's aromatic flower clusters, called umbels, display vibrant combinations of red, orange, yellow, blue, or white florets.

L. camara leaves, known for their distinct aroma, contain essential oils with reported insecticidal properties, serving as natural repellents against bees, mosquitoes, and flies. Furthermore, extracts, essential oils, leachates, residues, and rhizosphere soil from *L. camara* have demonstrated inhibitory effects on the germination and growth of other plant species (8).

HISTORY

L. camera, a species native to Central and South America, was introduced to Australia in 1841 as an ornamental plant. By the 1860s, it had become widespread in Sydney and Brisbane. Its distribution spans from Bega Shire in southern New South Wales (NSW) to Cape Melville in northern Queensland, and it is also found on Lord Howe and Norfolk Islands. The primary infestations are concentrated to the east of the Great Dividing Range in NSW and Queensland (9).

Pink-edged red lantana is commonly found in the following areas:

1. The North Coast, including regions around Kempsey, southeast of Dorrigo, Bellingen, and in the Coffs Harbour and Grafton areas (10).
2. Red varieties of lantana are found in the North Coast, particularly around Kempsey, Bellingen, and Coffs Harbour (10).
3. *L. camera* is unlikely to spread to new regions in NSW, though it continues to increase in density and expand within its current range (10).
4. The species originates from tropical and subtropical areas of Central and South America and was introduced to Australia as a decorative plant in the early 19th century (11).

Table 1: International Common names of *Lantana*

Country	Common names
Australia	Lantana, Pink-edgered lantana.
Brazil	cambara de espinto, Camara, Cidreirarana
Colombia	Sanguinaria, Venturosa, Gurupacha, Cariaquita, Carraquillo.
Canary Islands	Camara, Venturosa..
Cambodia	Ach man
China	Common lantana.
German	Wandelroeschen),
Guatemala	Yellow sage, ach man, White sage, Tembelekan, Talatala, Siete negritos, Prickly lantana, Pha-ka-krong, large leaf Lantana, Cuasquito, Cambara, deespinto, Bunga taya ayam.
Guyana	Sweet sage
India	Aruppu, Bunch berry, Gandheriya, <i>Lantana</i> , Pahj phuli, Wild stage
Jamaica	flowered sage.
Mexico	Skastajat stuki, Orozuz, orozus, Frutilla
Malaysia	angel lips, blacksage, bunga tayi .
Nicaragua	Cuasquito
Panama	Pasarin, Pasarrirn..
Rwanda	Maviyakuku.
Rodrigues islands	Vielle fille
Spanish	Galapagos Islands- prickly lantana, shrub verbean, supirrosa
Trinidad	white sage.
Thailand	Pha-ka-krong , Hedge flower, Phakaa drong
Tanzania	Kiwepe, Mkinda, Mvuti.
Tahiti	latora moa
USA	lantana, lantana wildtype, large leaf lantana.

MORPHOLOGY

Lantana camara is a vigorous, low-erect or subscandent shrub that grows between 1.2 and 2.4 metres (or even more). It has sturdy, recurved prickles with a pungent aroma of black currents. Its root system is very strong. Shrub with several branches that grows in clumps, thickets, or vines.

Stem: The stems are square-shaped, covered with tiny, backward-facing spines. The branches and stems have sharp angles, and spines grow along the edges in a curved arrangement.

Leaves: Opposing leaves grow along the stem, exhibiting a bright green hue, about 6 cm in length, with edges that are rounded and jagged.

Flowers: The flowers measure approximately 2.5 cm in diameter and come in an array of colours, such as light cream, yellow, white, pink, orange, red, lilac, and purple. Pollination occurs through butterflies and other insects.

Fruits: The fruits are glossy, rounded, and fleshy, ranging from blue to black in colour. When fully ripened, they turn purplish-black and measure around 3 mm in diameter.

Taxonomical Classification:

Kingdom	:	Plantae
Subkingdom	:	Tracheobionta
Superdivision	:	Spermatophytes
Division	:	Magnoliopsida
Subclass	:	Asteridae
Order	:	Lamiales
Family	:	Verbenaceae
Genus	:	<i>Lantana</i>
Species	:	<i>Lantana camara</i>

FAMILY

The Verbenaceae family, also known as the verbena family, is a diverse group of flowering plants belonging to the order Lamiales. It includes a variety of herbaceous plants, shrubs, trees, and vines, predominantly found in tropical and subtropical regions. The plants in this family often have simple, opposite, or whorled leaves and showy, tubular flowers that are usually pollinated by bees, butterflies, and birds.

Key genera within Verbenaceae include *Verbena* (known for ornamental species like *Verbena officinalis*), *Lantana* (noted for its colorful flowers and some invasive species), and *Gmelina* (important for timber). Many species in the family have economic uses in horticulture, herbal medicine, and as insect repellents.

GENIUS

The **genus *Lantana*** belongs to the family **Verbenaceae** and consists of about 150 species of flowering plants. It is widely distributed across tropical and subtropical regions of the world, particularly in the Americas, Africa, and Asia. *Lantana* species are often shrubs or small trees, known for their vibrant, colorful flowers that are typically arranged in clusters (12).

SPECIES

Lantana camara, commonly known as **common lantana**, **big-sage**, or **wild-sage**, is a species of flowering plant in the **Verbenaceae** family. Native to the American tropics, it has become widely naturalized in tropical and subtropical regions across the world, including parts of Africa, Asia, Australia, and the Pacific Islands. It is admired for its colorful flowers and is commonly used in landscaping, but it is also considered an invasive species in many areas due to its ability to spread rapidly and outcompete native vegetation (13).

Characterization

During the total bacterial count, the plate showing the highest number of colonies was selected for further investigation in all cases. The identification of bacterial genera was carried out based on morphological (cell shape and arrangement, size, Gram stain, and colony size, color, and shape on agar), physiological (oxygen relationship and motility), and biochemical (ammonia production, urease test, catalase test, starch hydrolysis, casein hydrolysis, H₂S production, NO₃ reduction, growth on nitrogenfree media, and growth on PSB media) characteristics, as outlined in *Bergey's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology* (Holt et al., 1994) (14).

Morphological Characterization

To examine the size and shape of bacterial cells, smears were prepared on slides, fixed by gentle heat, and stained with carbol fuchsin. Gram-stained bacterial cells on clean microscope slides were used to measure the bacterial size (length and width) using an ocular micrometer. After 24 hours of bacterial culture, smears were stained and examined under a microscope for cell shape and arrangement. Isolates were also examined for Gram-staining characteristics. The shape, size, and color of the colony were observed after streaking and incubating plates for 18-24 hours (15).

Physiological Characterization

To determine whether a culture is aerobic, nutrient broth containing 0.005% bromocresol purple was prepared in culture tubes. Observations were recorded at 48-hour intervals for 7 days. The hanging drop technique was used to demonstrate bacterial motility, utilizing a 12-hour-old nutrient broth culture (16).

Biochemical Characteristics

Ammonia Production: Cultures were incubated in peptone broth for 5 days. A small piece of filter paper soaked in Nessler's reagent was placed at the upper part of the culture tube. The test tube was warmed in a water bath at 50-60°C. A color change of the filter paper from brown to black indicated ammonia production.

Urease Test: The urease test was performed on urea agar medium. Basal medium was poured into flasks (90 ml per flask), autoclaved, and cooled to 45°C. Then, 10 ml of filter-sterilized 20% urea solution was added to each flask. After mixing, the medium was poured into 5 ml culture tubes. After solidifying in a slanted position, the tubes were inoculated with the test bacterium, incubated at $30 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, and observations were made at regular intervals for up to 15 days. A red color indicated the presence of urease, while a yellow color indicated its absence.

Catalase Test: The catalase test was performed by adding H₂O₂ to trypticase soy agar slants. The culture medium was poured into culture tubes, sterilized by autoclaving, and inoculated with the test bacterium. After incubation at 35°C for 24-48 hours, 3-4 drops of H₂O₂ were added to the culture slant. The appearance of gas bubbles indicated a positive catalase test.

Starch Hydrolysis: Starch hydrolysis was tested by adding 0.2% soluble starch to nutrient agar medium. The pH was adjusted to 7.0-7.2 using bromothymol blue as an indicator. The prepared medium was dispensed into test tubes, sterilized, and allowed to cool. After cooling, the cultures were inoculated and incubated at 30°C. Following incubation, a small portion of the liquid was treated with a diluted iodine solution. No color change indicated complete hydrolysis, a brown color indicated partial hydrolysis, and a blue color indicated no hydrolysis of starch.

Casein Hydrolysis: For casein hydrolysis, autoclaved and cooled basal medium was poured into sterilized Petri plates and inoculated with the culture. A single line streak inoculation was made across the surface of the medium, and the plates were incubated for 2-3 days at 37°C in an inverted position. A clear zone around the streak indicated a positive reaction, while the absence of a clear zone around the growth indicated a negative reaction.

Hydrogen Sulphide (H₂S) Production Test: The production of H₂S by different isolates was tested using filter paper strips impregnated with a 10% solution of lead acetate, which were then dried. A lead acetate strip was placed at the top of a nutrient broth culture and incubated. The appearance of blackening on the paper indicated H₂S production.

Nitrate Reduction: Nitrate reduction was tested using nitrate broth with the following composition:

10.0 g peptone, 5.0 g beef extract, 1.0 g KNO₃, and 1000 ml distilled water. The ingredients were dissolved, dispensed into tubes, and autoclaved. The broth was inoculated with the test

bacterium and incubated at 25°C. Reduction of nitrate was checked at regular intervals (up to 15 days) by adding a few drops of sulfanilic acid (0.8% in 5 M acetic acid) and dimethyl- α -naphthylamine (0.5% in 5 M acetic acid) to the nitrate broth culture. The presence of nitrite was indicated by the red color formed after the addition of these reagents (17).

PHYTOCHEMICALS:

Phytochemicals are naturally occurring chemical substances found in plants, often associated with potential health effects. These compounds, found in various plant species, are typically studied for their influence on human health. An exploration of the phytochemicals in *Lantana* species presents an opportunity to investigate a diverse array of unique chemical compounds. *Lantana camara* Linn, a toxic weed prevalent across multiple regions globally, including India, is one such plant of interest (18).

From the yellow-flowering variety of *Lantana camara*, eight triterpenoids were identified: betulonic acid, betulinic acid, oleanolic acid, lantadene A, lantadene B, icterogenin, lantanilic acid, and ursolic acid. Additionally, three flavonoids were isolated—hispidulin, pectolarigenin, and pectolarin— along with β -sitosterol-3-O- β D-glucoside, and a blend of campesterol, stigmasterol, and β -sitosterol (19). The most abundant compounds among them included germacrene D (24.50–6.15%), biciclogermacrene (33.32–14.27%), spathulenol (25.04–1.06%), eremophilene (20.64–1.93%), valecene (33.70–0.84%), viridiflorene (19.46%), and 1,10-di-epi-cubenol (27.93–21.32%). These findings suggest the presence of distinct chemotypes within *L. camara* (20).

PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITY:

Antihemorrhoidal Effects:

The antihemorrhoidal properties of *Lantana camara* were evaluated in 20 patients with 1st and 2nd-degree hemorrhoids, using capsules containing a dry aqueous extract of *L. camara* (500 mg/kg) and lactose (100 mg/kg). The findings indicated a significant reduction in the symptoms of acute hemorrhoidal flare-ups, such as bleeding, anal discomfort, discharge, swelling, pain during prolapse, and proctitis, after 28 days of treatment. No noteworthy adverse effects were observed (21).

Antithrombin Activity:

Methanolic extracts derived from the leaves of *Lantana camara* have demonstrated the ability to inhibit human thrombin, indicating potential antithrombotic effects. (22)

Anti-hypertensive Effects:

Hypertension is a prevalent cardiovascular condition and a significant public health concern, with its prevalence steadily increasing in the Indian subcontinent. Recent studies show a 30% rise in hypertension rates in urban populations and a 10% increase in rural areas over the past three decades (23). *Lantana camara*, also known as “Spanish flag” or “West Indian Lantana,” is commonly found in ornamental gardens. It features aromatic leaves and vibrant flowers in hues of orange, blue, red, yellow, and bright red, along with dark blue and black drupes. The plant, particularly its leaves, is recognized for its anti-tumor, antibacterial, anti-hypertensive, tonic, and expectorant properties. Additionally, the roots of *L. camara* are traditionally used to treat rheumatism (24).

Antifilarial Activity:

The crude extract of *L. camara* stems has shown significant antifilarial effects. Both the whole extract and its chloroform fraction led to the death of adult *Brugia malayi* and sterilized most of the surviving female worms in the rodent model, *Mastomys coucha*.

Anti-inflammatory Activity:

The aqueous extract of *L. camara* demonstrated notable anti-inflammatory properties in albino rats. Treatment with 500 mg/kg body weight of the extract significantly reduced paw volume in the carrageenan-induced paw edema test (25).

Antiuroolithiasis Activity:

Various extracts from *L. camara* leaves were assessed for their antiuroolithiasis effects in male albino rats, induced with ethylene glycol and ammonium chloride to cause calcium oxalate urolithiasis. These extracts significantly decreased the deposition of calcium and oxalate and reduced urinary excretion of calcium, oxalate, and creatinine (26).

Anticancer and Antiproliferative Activity:

Several parts of *L. camara* have been investigated for anticancer and antiproliferative activities. The leaves, in particular, demonstrated antiproliferative effects against Hep-2 (laryngeal cancer) and NCI-H292 (lung cancer) cell lines. In vitro tests using the MTT assay revealed that the methanol extract of *L. camara* leaves reduced cell viability in NCI-H292 cells by 25.8%. Additionally, the leaves displayed cytotoxicity against the Vero cell line. Oleanonic acid, isolated from *L. camara*, showed promising cytotoxicity against A375 (malignant skin melanoma), Hep2 (epidermoid laryngeal carcinoma), and U937 (lymphoma) cell lines (27,28).

Antimicrobial Activity:

Extracts from various parts of *L. camara*, including leaves, stems, roots, flowers, and seeds, have demonstrated effective antimicrobial properties. Aqueous, ethanol, and methanol extracts from these plant parts exhibited significant antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Vibrio cholerae*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* through disc diffusion and microdilution methods. The antifungal activity was tested against *Alternaria* species, which cause diseases in vegetables, using the food poison plate method. At a 20 mg/ml dose, *L. camara* showed strong antifungal effects. Ethanol extracts were particularly potent against white and brown rot fungi, even at low concentrations (29-31).

Antimotility Activity:

L. camara has exhibited significant antimotility effects, demonstrated by a study on the methanol extract of the leaves. A 1 g/kg body weight dose was administered to mice, resulting in complete inhibition of intestinal motility as assessed by the charcoal meal test. Additionally, intraperitoneal administration of the extract at doses of 125 and 250 mg/kg significantly reduced fecal production in castor oil-induced diarrhea in mice. (32-34).

Antiulcerogenic Activity:

The methanol extract of *L. camara* leaves has been shown to possess antiulcerogenic properties, particularly in rats with gastric lesions induced by aspirin, ethanol, and cold restraint stress. When rats were pre-treated with doses of 200 and 400 mg/kg body weight of the extract, a significant protective effect was observed against ulcers caused by aspirin, ethanol, and cold stress. The extract demonstrated a dose-dependent antiulcer effect in all experimental models (35-37).

Hemolytic Activity:

The hemolytic potential of *L. camara* aqueous extract and its solvent fractions was evaluated using a spectroscopic method across various concentrations (125, 250, 500, 1000 µg/ml). The results indicated that the extract exhibited minimal hemolytic activity against human erythrocytes (38,39).

Antihyperglycemic Activity:

Several extracts of *L. camara*, including the methanol extract of leaves and the aqueous extract of roots, have been demonstrated to have effective antihyperglycemic effects. In alloxan-induced diabetic rats, oral administration of the methanol extract of *L. camara* leaves (400 mg/kg body weight) resulted in a significant reduction in blood glucose levels (121.94 mg/dl). Additionally, the extract contributed to improvements in body weight, HbA1c levels, and liver cell regeneration (37,39,40).

Wound Healing Activity:

The aqueous extract of *L. camara* leaves has been reported to promote wound healing in rats. A dose of 100 mg/kg/day significantly accelerated wound contraction (98%), enhanced collagen synthesis, and reduced healing time. Moreover, the ethanol extract of *L. camara* leaves has also been noted for its wound healing effects in adult male Wistar rats (36,40).

Conclusion

Lantana camara, a tropical plant native to Central and South America, has emerged as a significant subject of study due to its diverse medicinal properties and extensive use in traditional medicine. While it is widely known for its ornamental value, *L. camara* also possesses potent therapeutic potential that spans a broad spectrum of biological activities. These include anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, antimicrobial, anti-hypertensive, and antidiabetic effects, among others. The plant's rich phytochemical profile, which includes triterpenoids, flavonoids, and essential oils, contributes to its varied pharmacological benefits, making it an invaluable asset for both modern and traditional medicinal practices.

Research on *Lantana camara* has demonstrated its efficacy in treating ailments such as hemorrhoids, hypertension, malaria, skin rashes, and cancer. Moreover, its antimicrobial and antifungal properties position it as a natural remedy for infections, further expanding its therapeutic utility. The plant's role in wound healing and gastrointestinal health, alongside its promising anti-thrombin and anti-ulcerogenic properties, underscores its diverse range of applications.

Despite its potential, it is important to acknowledge that *L. camara* is also classified as an invasive species in many regions, necessitating careful management to prevent environmental harm. Future research should focus on optimizing the safe use of this plant, particularly formulating natural remedies and treatments, while addressing concerns related to its invasiveness.

In conclusion, *Lantana camara* stands as a multifaceted medicinal plant with immense potential for health and wellness applications. Continued exploration of its phytochemical composition and pharmacological properties will likely yield valuable insights, offering new therapeutic avenues for the treatment of a wide range of diseases. However, it is crucial to balance its medicinal use with ecological responsibility to mitigate its impact on local biodiversity.

REFERENCE

1. Kumarasamyraja D, Jeganathan NS and Manavalan R: Pharmacological review of *Lantana camara* L. International Journal of Pharm Res 2012; 2: 1-5.
2. Ghisalberti EL: *Lantana camara* Linn. Review Fitoterapia 2000; 71: 467-485.
3. Sharma OP, Makkar HPS, Dawra RK, A review of the noxious plant *Lantana camara*. Toxicon 1988;26(11):975-987.
4. Sanders RW, The genera of Verbenaceae in the Southeastern United States. Harvard Papers Bot. 2001;5(2):303-358.
5. Day MD, Wiley CJ, Playford J, Zalucki MP. *Lantana*: Current Management Status and future prospects. Australian Centre for International Agricultural Research: Canberra 2003.
6. Rakesh K. Josh. William N. Setzer Valdir F. da Veiga Junior “Aromatic and medicinal plants with anti-diabetic potential from India: A review” American Journal of Essential Oils and Natural Products; Vol. 2 (4): 22-28 2015.
7. O. Oluwadayo Sonibare* and I. Effiong “Antibacterial activity and cytotoxicity of essential oil of *Lantana Camara* L. leaves from Nigeria” African Journal of Biotechnology Vol. 7 (15),2618-2620,2008.
8. Patel Jitendra, Qureshi Md Shamim, Kumar GS, Kumar D, Kumar K Ashok. Phytochemicals and Pharmacological activities of *Lantana Camara* Linn. 2010.
9. Bhatt, N., Gupta, P.K., Naithani, S. (2011). Ceric-induced grafting of Acrylonitrile onto Alpha Cellulose isolated from *Lantana camara*. Cell. Chem. Techn, 45, 321-327.
10. Kensa, V.M. (2011). Studies on phytochemical screening and antibacterial activities of *Lantana camara* Linn. *Pl. Sci. Fe., 1*, 74-79.
11. Zhang, M., Liu, X., O'Neill, M. (2002). Spectral discrimination of Phytophthora infestants infection on tomatoes based on principal component and cluster analyses. *Int., Jou., Rem., Sens., 23*, 1095-1107.
12. Girish C. S. Negi, Subrat Sharma Subash, C.R. Vishvakarma, Sher S. Samant, Rakesh K. Maikhuri, Ram C. Prasad and Lok M.S. Palni, Ecology and use of *Lantana camera* in india;May 6, 2019.
13. Ghisalberti, E. L[2000] . “*Lantana camera* l. [Verbenaceae]”. *Fitoterapia*. 71 [5]; 467-486. 14. Holt JG, Krieg NR, Sneath PHA, Staley JT, Williams ST. Holt JG, Krieg NR, Sneath PHA, Staley JT, Williams ST.
15. Chhonkar PK, Bhadraray S, Patra AK, Purakayastha TJ. Experiments in soil biology biochemistry, Westville publishing house, New Delhi, 2007.
16. Aneja KR. Experiments in Microbiology. 4th edition of cultivation techniques for Isolation and Enumeration of microorganisms. New age International Publishers. New Delhi, 2007, 157-188.

17. Rajan K Ojha, Amrit K Jha and Sudhir K Jha, Microbial community on leaf surface of *Lantana camara* as influenced by industrial and road side pollution. 2019.
18. Qureshi Md. Shamim, Patel Jitendra, Venkateshwar Reddy A, Syed Safiullah and P Mohapatra. Phytochemicals and Pharmacological Activities of *Moringa oleifera* Lam. Research J. Pharmacology and Pharmacodynamics. 2010; 2(2):183-186.
19. Fu-Chiang Juang, Yu-Fang Chen, Fuh-Mei Lin and Keh-Feng Huang. Constituents from the leaves of *Lantana camara* (iv). J Chin Med. 2005;16(2-3): 149-155.
20. Erlânio O. Sousa, Aracelio V. Colares, Fabiola F. G. Rodrigues, Adriana R. Campos, Sidney G. Lima and José Galberto M. Costa. Effect of Collection Time on Essential Oil Composition of *Lantana camara* Linn (Verbenaceae) Growing in Brazil Northeastern, Rec. Nat. Prod. 2010;4(1):31-37.
21. Gidwani BK, Bhargava S, Rao SP, Majoomdar A, Pawar DP, Alaspure RN. Analgesic, antiinflammatory and antihemorrhoidal activity of aqueous extract of *Lantana camara* Linn. Res J Pharm Tech 2009; 2:378-81.
22. . O'Neill MJ, Lewis JA, Noble HM, Holland S, Mansat C, Farthing JE, et al. Isolation of translactone-containing triterpenes with thrombin inhibitory activities from the leaves of *Lantana camara*. J Nat Prod 1998; 61:1328-31.
23. Reddy NM. "*Lantana Camara* Linn. Chemical Constituents and Medicinal Properties" Vol. 2 (6)445-8, 2013.
24. Rohit Gundamaraju, Sartaj Banu Mulaplli, Dr.Ramesh.C."Evaluation of Anti-Obesity Activity of *Lantana camara* Var Linn. by Progesterone Induced Obesity on Albino Mice" . IJPPR Vol.4 (4) 213-218 2012-1.
25. Gidwani BK et al. Analgesic, anti-inflammatory and antihemorrhoidal activity of aqueous extract of *Lantana Camara*.
26. Mayee R, Thosar A; Evaluation of *Lantana camara* Linn. (*Verbenaceae*) for antiurolithiatic and antioxidant activities in rats. International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research, 2011; 3 (1):10-14.
27. Gomes de Melo J, de Sousa Araújo TA, ThijianNobre de Almeida e Castro V, Lyra de Vasconcelos Cabral D, do Desterro Rodrigues M, Carneiro do Nascimento S et al.; Antiproliferative activity, antioxidant capacity and tannin content in plants of semi-arid Brazil. Molecules, 2010; 15 (12): 8534-42.
28. Pour BM, Latha LY and Sasidharan S;Cytotoxicity and oral acute toxicity studies of *Lantana camara* leaf extract. Molecules, 2011; 16 (5): 3663-3674.
29. Kalita, S. (2011). Phytochemical composition and *in vitro* hemolytic activity of *Lantana camara* (Verbenaceae) leaves. *Pharmacologyonline*, 1(7), 59-67.
30. Prasad, A.M., Iverson, L.R., Liaw, A. (2006). Newer classification and regression techniques: bagging and random forests for ecological prediction. *Eco.*, 9, 181–199.

31. Sharma, S., Singh, A., Sharma, O.P. (1999). An improved procedure for isolation and purification of lantadene A, the bioactive pentacyclic triterpenoid from *Lantana camara* leaves. *Jour. Medi. Aro. Pla. Sci.*, 21, 686–688.
32. Achhireddy, N.R., Singh, S.M., Achhireddy, L.L., Nigg, H.N., Nagy, S.S. (1985). Isolation and partial characterization of phytotoxic compounds from *Lantana camara* L.). *Jour. Chem. Eco*, 11, 979–988.
33. Begum, S., Wahab, A., Siddiqui, B.S. (2000). Pentacyclic triterpenoids from the aerial parts of *Lantana camara*. *Chem. Pharm. Bul*, 51, 134-137.
34. Bhatt, N., Gupta, P.K., Naithani, S. (2011). Ceric-induced grafting of Acrylonitrile onto Alpha Cellulose isolated from *Lantana camara*. *Cell. Chem. Techn*, 45, 321-327.
35. Bhatt, Y.D., Rawat, Y.S., Singh, S.P. (1994). Changes in ecosystem functioning after replacement of forest by *Lantana* shrubland in Kumaon Himalaya. *Jour. Veg. Sci*, 5, 67– 70.
36. Chopra, R.N., Nayar, S.L., Chopra, I.C. (1956). *Glossary of Indian medicinal plants*. CSIR New Delhi, India.
37. Day, M.D., Wiley, C.J., Playford, J.J., Zalucki, M.P. (2003). *Lantana: Current Management, Status and Future Prospects*. *Aust. Cen. Inter. Agri. Res*, 5, 1- 20.
38. Ganjewala, D.D., Sam, S., Khan, K.H. (2009). Biochemical compositions and antibacterial activities of *Lantana camara* plants with yellow, lavender, red and white flowers. *Eur. Jour. Bio.*, 3, 69-77.
39. Kensa, V.M. (2011). Studies on phytochemical screening and antibacterial activities of *Lantana camara* Linn. *Pl. Sci. Fe.*, 1, 74-79.
40. Zhang, M., Liu, X., O'Neill, M. (2002). Spectral discrimination of *Phytophthora* infestants infection on tomatoes based on principal component and cluster analyses. *Int., Jou., Rem., Sens.*, 23, 1095-1107.